

Table 2: List of marine animals mentioned from interviews with local experts in Levuka town, Levuka Vaka Viti, Vatukalo village and Tokou village. Sorted in alphabetical order of Fijian local name.

IUCN world status abbreviations: LC = Least Concern, **VU = Vulnerable**, **NT = Near Threatened**, **EN = Endangered**, **CR = Critically Endangered**, **DD = Data Deficient**

Colour		Denotes				
		Not available on Table by MOF Levuka				
		Fijian name not mentioned by interviewee				
Fijian name	Fish grade	IUCN Status	English common name	Scientific name / taxonomy	Reef passages / areas where this fish is observed or caught	Other comments on this fish
		EN	Whale shark	<i>Rhincodon typus</i>	Nailobaloba	Locally referred to as "whale shark"
		LC	Albacore Tuna	<i>Thunnus alalunga</i>	Deep seas, outside the reef passages	Also called "Yatuloa"
		LC	Yellowfin Tuna	<i>Thunnus albacares</i>	Deep seas, outside the reef passages	Referred to as "yellow-fin tuna" locally. Also called "Yatu-ni-toga"
		LC	Skipjack Tuna	<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>	Deep seas, outside the reef passages	Also called "Yatuvuai" and "Yatusewa"
Babale		LC	Dolphin (generally)	<i>Stenella</i> sp.	Natubari, Nailobaloba, Nalulu	Generic Fijian name for dolphins. Indicator of bad weather when sighted in the lagoon and inside the reef passage
Babaloa		LC	Emperor	<i>Lethrinus</i> sp.	Nuku, Nailobaloba, Natubari, Waitovu, Toki	A type of Sabutu. Name of Sabutu when it is big.
Balagi	C	LC	Yellowfin Surgeonfish	<i>Acanthurus xanthopterus</i>	Natubari, Cule reef, Cakauseva, Balavu reef, Loloi reef, Nukutabua	Also referred to as "Balaginawa." Mostly caught on the reef
Bati	C	LC	Two-spot red snapper	<i>Lutjanus bohar</i>	Nailobaloba	Prone to ciguatoxin (fish poisoning) when in season around October. Also called "Baji"
Bu	A	LC	Humpnose Big-eye bream	<i>Monotaxis grandoculis</i>	Nailobaloba, Natubari	Also called "Mama"
Corocoro	C	LC	Blotcheye soldierfish, Squirrelfish	<i>Myripristis berndti</i> , <i>Sargocentron</i> spp.	Nalulu	Refer to Holocentridae fishes which are red and have big eyes. Totem fish for Lekorokoro village, it is a small red fish. Also called "Matalevu"
Cucu	C	LC	Indian goatfish	<i>Parupeneus indicus</i>	Nalulu	Also called "Daunau"
Cula-ni-natu		LC	Humpback red snapper	<i>Lutjanus gibbus</i>	Natubari	Another name for "Sabutu-damu"
Damu	C	LC	Mangrove red snapper	<i>Lutjanus agentimaculatus</i>	Toki, Nuku, Nailobaloba	Best to catch in day time at 30-40m depths
Dokoni	A	LC	Longface emperor	<i>Lethrinus olivaceus</i>	Nalulu, Gavo	Also referred to as "Dokonivudi"
Donu	B	LC	Leopard coral grouper, red salmon cod	<i>Plectropomus leopardus</i>	Nailobaloba, Toki, Nalulu, Gavo, Kalavo, Natubari, Cakauseva	Also called "Droudroua"
Dridri-ni-toga	C	LC	Lined surgeonfish	<i>Acanthurus lineatus</i>	Mostly caught on the reef	Also called "Meto"
Droudroua	B	LC	Leopard coral grouper, red salmon cod	<i>Plectropomus leopardus</i>	Nailobaloba, Toki, Nalulu, Gavo, Kalavo, Natubari, Cakauseva	Also called "Donu"
Dulutoga		LC	Barracuda	<i>Sphyrna</i> sp.	Nalulu, Gavo, Kalavo	Name for the young Ogo. Dulutoga could also refer to <i>Sphyrna forsteri</i> (Forster's seapike ["Silasila"])
Kabatia	C	LC	Emperor	<i>Lethrinus</i> spp.	Nailobaloba, Nuku, Toki, Waitovu, Natubari, Nalulu, Gavo	Can refer to multiple Lethrinids. Totem fish for Vatukalo. Can be found/caught in all passages and reefs
Kacika	A	LC	Yellowlip emperor	<i>Lethrinus xanthochilus</i>	Natubari	Also called "Kasika"
Kake	C	LC	Russels snapper	<i>Lutjanus russelli</i>	Caught in Cawaci reef, Navusovuso, Nasuko, in front of Ovalau resort and Toki village	Also called "Kwake"
Kanace	B	LC	Mullet (generally)	<i>Mugil</i> spp., <i>Moolgarda</i> spp.	Caught closer to shore with mostly spear	Generic Fijian name for mullets. Called "Wailo" when smaller.
Kavu	B	DD	Giant grouper	<i>Epinephelus lanceolatus</i>	Natubari	Caught near Levuka wharf
Kawago	A	LC	Spangled emperor	<i>Lethrinus nebulosus</i>	Nailobaloba	
Kawakawa	A	Depends on species	Grouper (generally)	<i>Epinephelus</i> spp., <i>Cephalopholis</i> spp.	Nailobaloba, Nuku, Navusovuso, Toki, Waitovu, Natubari, Nalulu, Gavo, Kalavo	Can refer to many species of grouper
Maimai		LC	Common Dolphinfish	<i>Coryphaena hippurus</i>	Waitovu, Toki, Nuku, Nailobaloba	Generic Fijian name for dolphinfish. Also called "Mahi mahi"
Mama	A	LC	Humpnose Big-eye bream	<i>Monotaxis grandoculis</i>	Nailobaloba	Also called "Bu"
Meto	C	LC	Striated surgeonfish	<i>Ctenochaetus striatus</i>	Mostly caught on the reef	Also called "Dridri." Can refer to two different species.
Nuqa	A	LC	Rabbitfish (generally)	<i>Siganus</i> spp.	Nailobaloba, Nuku, Navusovuso, Toki, Waitovu, Natubari, Nalulu, Gavo ("found everywhere")	Generic Fijian name for siganids. Mostly caught in nearshore reefs, around estuaries, near the mangroves ("vei-dogo") and swampy areas and not specifically reef passages.
Nuqalevu	A	LC	Vermiculated spinefoot	<i>Siganus vermiculatus</i>	Nailobaloba, Nuku, Navusovuso, Toki, Waitovu, Natubari, Nalulu, Gavo ("found everywhere")	Also known as "Volaca," "Nuqa-ni-baravi" and "Nuqa."
Nuqa-ni-baravi	A	LC	Vermiculated spinefoot	<i>Siganus vermiculatus</i>	Nailobaloba, Nuku, Navusovuso, Toki, Waitovu, Natubari, Nalulu, Gavo ("found everywhere")	Also known as "Volaca," "Nuqalevu" and "Nuqa." Mostly caught in nearshore reefs, around estuaries, near the mangroves (vei-dogo) and swampy areas and not specifically in reef passages.
Ogo	C	LC	Great barracuda	<i>Sphyrna barracuda</i>	Nailobaloba, Nuku, Navusovuso, Toki, Waitovu, Natubari, Nalulu, Gavo	Can refer to multiple species. Also known as "Ogolevu."
Pakapaka	A	LC	Jobfish (generally)	<i>Pristipomoides</i> spp., <i>Etelis</i> spp.	Caught in the deep bottom / sea.	Generic Fijian name for <i>Pristipomoides</i> spp., and <i>Etelis</i> spp. Can refer to multiple species of Jobfish and Lutjanids. Caught in the deep sea/bottom at ~40-50m depth
Qio		Depends on species	Shark (generally)	Selachimorpha, <i>Carcharhinus</i> spp., <i>Sphyrna</i> spp.	Natubari (Levuka passage), Nailobaloba, Waitovu	Generic Fijian name for sharks.
Qio		VU	White-tip reef shark	<i>Triaenodon obesus</i>	Nailobaloba	
Qio		NT	Tiger shark	<i>Galeocerdo cuvier</i>	Nailobaloba	Also called "Qio-saqa"
Qio		CR	Hammerhead shark (generally)	<i>Sphyrna</i> spp.	Nailobaloba	Also called "Qio-ulu-tuki." All species threatened (CR – VU).
Qio-saqa		VU	Bull shark	<i>Carcharhinus leucas</i>	Natubari, Nailobaloba	Mostly seen near the Levuka Wharf
Regua		LC	Blubberlip snapper	<i>Lutjanus rivulatus</i>	Nailobaloba	Prone to seasonal ciguatoxins (fish poisoning).
Rosiloa	A	LC	Timor snapper	<i>Lutjanus timoriensis</i>	Nailobaloba	
Rosinibogi	A	LC	Malabar blood snapper	<i>Lutjanus malabaricus</i>	Toki	
Sabutu	A	LC	Emperor or Bream (generally), Pacific yellowtail emperor	Lethrinidae, <i>Lethrinus obsoletus</i> , <i>Lethrinus atkinsoni</i>	Toki, Nuku, Nailobaloba, Navusovuso, Waitovu, Natubari, Nalulu, Gavo, Kalavo	Can refer to multiple species of Emperor/Bream. Can be caught/found all throughout the year
Sabutu-damu		LC	Humpback red snapper	<i>Lutjanus gibbus</i>	Nalulu	Also called "Bo," "Yabo," "Taen"
Sabutukula	A	LC	Pacific yellowtail emperor, Mozambique large-eye bream	<i>Lethrinus atkinsoni</i> , <i>Wattsia mossambica</i>	Nuku, Nailobaloba, Natubari, Waitovu, Toki, Nalulu	Can refer to two species. Also referred to as "Sabutu"
Sabutuvula		LC	Emperor	<i>Lethrinus</i> sp.	Nalulu, Gavo, Kalavo, Nuku, Nailobaloba, Natubari, Waitovu, Toki	Another name for "Sabutu"
Saqa	B	LC	Trevally (generally)	<i>Caranx</i> sp., <i>Carangoides</i> sp.	Nailobaloba, Nuku, Navusovuso, Toki, Waitovu, Natubari, Nalulu, Gavo	Generic Fijian name for Carangidae.
Saqadrau	B	LC	Bigeye Trevally	<i>Caranx sexfasciatus</i>	Nailobaloba, Nuku	
Saqaleka	B	LC	Giant Trevally	<i>Caranx ignobilis</i>	Nailobaloba, Nuku, Nalulu, Gavo, Kalavo	Also called "Saqalevu"
Saqalao	B	LC	Black jack	<i>Caranx lugubris</i>	Nalulu, Gavo, Kalavo	
Saqanivatu	B	LC	Bluefin Trevally	<i>Caranx melampygus</i>	Nailobaloba, Nuku	Also called "Tauta," "Saqa-dina"
Sucuwalu		VU	White teatfish	<i>Holothuria fuscogilva</i>	In front of Vatukalo, in the lagoon, "deep blue area"	Also referred to as "Dri"
Ta	C	LC	Surgeonfish (generally)	<i>Naso</i> spp., <i>Acanthurus</i> spp.	Toki, Natubari	Generic Fijian name for Acanthurids.
Ta-lele	C	LC	Bluespine Unicornfish	<i>Naso unicornis</i>	Toki, Natubari	Also called "Ta-peni-kau," "Jivijivi" or "tivitivi," "Ta"
Ta-masimasi		LC	Brown Unicornfish	<i>Acanthurus</i> sp.	Toki, Natubari	Referred to brown surgeonfish when small.
Ta-peni-kau	C	LC	Bluespine Unicornfish	<i>Naso unicornis</i>	Natubari	Also called "Ta-lele," "Jivijivi" or "tivitivi," "Ta"
Tovuto		Depends on species	Whale (generally)	Balaenopteridae	Natubari (Levuka passage), Nailobaloba, Nalulu	Generic Fijian name for whales. Seen in cold season. Seen travelling in Natubari passage and around Levuka. Last seen in August-October, 2025.
Tovuto		LC	Humpback whale	<i>Megaptera novaeangliae</i>	Natubari (Levuka passage), Nailobaloba	
Tovuto		VU	Sperm whale	<i>Physeter macrocephalus</i>	Nailobaloba	
Ulavi	C	LC	Parrotfish (generally)	<i>Hipposcarus</i> spp.; <i>Chlorurus</i> spp.; <i>Scarus</i> spp.; <i>Cetoscarus</i> spp.; <i>Leptoscarus</i> sp.; <i>Calotomus</i> sp.	Nailobaloba, Nuku, Navusovuso, Toki, Waitovu, Natubari, Nalulu, Gavo, Kalavo	Generic Fijian name for parrotfish. Caught/observed in all reefs using spearguns, not caught specifically in the reef passages
Uluqa	A	LC	Saddle-back snapper; Cocoa snapper	<i>Paracaesio kusakarii</i> ; <i>Paracaesio stonei</i>	Nailobaloba	Can refer to two species.
Ulurua	C	LC	Steephead parrotfish	<i>Chlorurus microrhinos</i>	Nalulu, Gavo, Natubari	
Vilu	B	LC	Blue Trevally	<i>Carangoides ferdau</i>	Nailobaloba, Nuku	Referred to as just "Vilu"
Vilu-saqa	B	LC	Shadow Trevally	<i>Carangoides dinema</i>	Nailobaloba, Nuku	
Wailo		LC	Mullet	<i>Moolgarda</i> spp., <i>Mugil</i> spp.	Caught closer to shore with mostly spears	When "Kanace" is small it is called "Wailo." Wailo is the totem fish for Tokou.
Walu	A	NT	Spanish Mackerel	<i>Scomberomorus commerson</i>	Gavo, Nailobaloba, Waitovu, Toki, Nuku, Kalavo. Caught in Vatu, close to Makogai, Naigani.	Caught not that far from the reef, in 2-4m depth. During Christmas – New Years' time, the stomach of the Walu gets bigger
Wau	A	LC	Wahoo	<i>Acanthocybium solandri</i>	Waitovu, Nailobaloba, Nuku, Toki	Can be found 100-200 meters away from any reef